

SITUATION OF APPLICATION OF DIVERGENT TECHNOLOGIES IN BUSINESS ECONOMY

Utkirov Anvar Utkirovich

Independent researcher of Karshi State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13342167>

Abstract: This article examines the process of creating a database of divergent technologies for enterprises. The database plays an important role in managing technological processes and increasing the efficiency of the enterprise. The possibilities of data collection, analysis and management through the use of digital technologies and information systems are analyzed. Ways to increase competitiveness of enterprises through the introduction of innovative technologies are also highlighted.

Keywords: Divergent technologies, database, enterprises, technological processes, information systems, digital technologies, data management, innovative development.

Today, the theme of the ecological type of reproduction is becoming more and more relevant. Here, we must understand that human encroachment on nature has deepened so much that as a result, irreversible processes are occurring that have a negative impact on people's lives. The promotion of the ecological type of economic activity, which represents the application of various measures of influence for the violation of existing regulations, is also considered as one of the topical issues.

Systematic measures to increase the competitiveness of the national economy have been established, which initially include supporting enterprises exporting goods and products in the real sector, ensuring their competitiveness in foreign markets, applying strict economy, and encouraging the reduction of product costs and expenses. incentives, including the implementation of an effective system of energy saving and measures to reduce energy capacity, stimulation of gross demand in the domestic market, etc. were defined.

We believe that the following conclusions and proposals of the endogenous economic growth theory schools are useful for the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of the transition to an innovative economy. To them:

- ensuring economic growth depends on the conditions of free competition in the economy, mobility of the workforce, opportunities for companies to enter and exit the market, constantly improving their products and technologies, offering new innovative products and gaining a foothold in the market. . These

goods and technologies then spread throughout the economy, stimulating general labor productivity growth;

- ensuring accelerated economic growth depends on the openness of the economy, the possibility of producing modern technological goods and services due to the attraction of direct foreign investment. Integration into the world education system and science, involvement of leading specialists from developed western countries in the process of reproduction;

- in the process of developing personnel training in the educational system, adapting it to market requirements, training personnel for modern technologies and, first of all, the digital economy - is a prerequisite for increasing labor productivity;

- economic growth requires respect for the environment. Environmental pollution not only leads to deterioration of the standard of living of the population, but also becomes a heavy burden for the economy;

- it is necessary to create market institutions that operate efficiently in the economy. To develop the economy, it cannot attract a large amount of investment without market institutions that operate efficiently and protect the interests of private property. Such institutions require a political system with competing structures that ensure the rule of law and stability.

Innovative economic growth occurs at the expense of growth of GDP and improvement of its composition, qualitative renewal of used production factors, improvement of technology and human and intellectual capital. The main factors are innovative investments, incentives, the structure of knowledge and skill development institutions, the structural theoretical types of the use of divergent technologies in increasing the economic efficiency of enterprises, structural theoretical types are described as follows: Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Types of mechanisms of economic growth and stimulation of state-owned enterprises

Wide use of innovations with a technological basis, stimulation of production and organization of economic activity, determines the actual existence of an institutional and competitive environment encouraging innovative activity in the domestic economic system. Innovative investments that ensure the continuous renewal of the production base and the continuous production of new products play an important role in achieving the quality of sustainable economic growth and ultimately improving the welfare of society. The development of the innovative economy is based on the renewal of production, which is practically impossible without additional property, money and intellectual investments in the production activity itself.

Thus, according to the criteria of convergent (and divergent) structural changes, the characteristics of the description of the action of the factors of connection are considered as distinguishing features:

1. Criteria of reproduction (accumulation rate, autonomous investments, age and obsolescence of fixed capital, accelerated depreciation). These criteria are considered to be an assessment of the possibilities of modernization of the industry and industrial "leaps" - renewal of gross means of production and radical increase of labor productivity, increase of GDP due to updating of new generations of equipment and technology.

2. The criteria of sensitivity of the economy to innovations (invention commercialization intensity, innovation transfer). With the help of these criteria, it is possible to assess the technological perfect fit of the economy. As a final result, positive changes in the technological structure are expressed in changes in the structural structure of the produced added value, the economic efficiency of the firm, and the composition of social groups.

3. Diversification criteria (types and sources of investments, including sectoral and technological diversification of production of foreign investments, dependence on imports). These criteria indicate the possibility of technological modernization of the economy to the level of the most developed countries.

4. Market criteria (the share of loss-making enterprises, the ratio of the share of public and private investments in the innovative sector, the share of small and large businesses in it, the state of the business support infrastructure). The purpose of this criterion is to determine the level of development of market mechanisms in the field of innovative entrepreneurship, and its impact on positive structural structural changes.

5. Social criteria (indicators of the quantity and quality of the labor force in the field of innovative research and development), with which it is possible to assess the potential for increasing the efficiency of the gross labor factor in the economy.

6. Institutional criteria (effective tax innovation incentives in high-tech industries, state guarantees and subsidies, the existence of public-private partnerships) indicate the norms and rules that determine the movement of inter-industry and inter-industry capital.

References:

1. Ishmuhamedov A.E. va bosh. Milliy va xalqaro iqtisodiyot: Darslik. - T.: 2010.-316 b.
2. Максимова В.Ф. Микроэкономика: учебник. - М.: Маркет ДС, 2010.-368 с.
3. В.Я. Горфинкеля, В.А. Швандара. Экономика предприятия. Учебник для вузов. - М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2007.- 456 с.
4. Фаррух Қодиров. АҲОЛИГА ТИББИЙ ХИЗМАТ КЎРСАТИШДАН ОЛИНГАН ДАРОМАД ВА ХАРАЖАТЛАРНИ ИМИТАЦИОН МОДЕЛИ. TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI "O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ILMIY. 922
5. Qodirov, F. E. "Methodological aspects and importance of development of medical services through econometric modeling and forecasting options."

6. Фаррух Қодиров. Аҳолига хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасининг моделлаштиришни тизимли имитация қилиш. Biznes-Эксперт. 2022, Biznes-Эксперт ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ 1736 №56 ст 102-106
7. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "CREATION OF ELECTRONIC MEDICAL BASE WITH THE HELP OF SOFTWARE PACKAGES FOR MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 128-130.
8. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "IMPORTANCE OF KASH-HEALTH WEB PORTAL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 80-83.
9. Qodirov, Farrux, and Muxlisa Mavlonova. "RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUDUDLARDA XIZMAT KO 'RSATISH TURLARINI OSHIRISH." Молодые ученые 2.6 (2024): 110-113.

